

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*A non-profit environmental
research center affiliated
with the
University of Bergen*

*Edv. Griegsv. 3a
N-5037 Bergen, Norway
Tel: +47 55 29 72 88
Fax: +47 55 20 00 50*

Technical Report No. 149

**An ERS SAR slick discrimination
algorithm**

by

Heidi Espedal

May, 1998

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Executive Summary

The objective of this work has been to develop a standard procedure including tools, to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process with focus on oil spills. The supervised algorithm includes:

1. initial processing of SAR imagery
2. slick detection and direct analysis
3. contextual analysis
4. model results
5. how to draw conclusions based on the combined results.

The developed procedures are described by means of simple flow charts and additional explanatory text. Tests were performed using 124 slicks in SAR imagery. These included 34 confirmed oil spills, 5 confirmed natural films, 5 confirmed non-oil pollutions (3 factories and 2 platforms). For the remaining cases, prior classifications made by experienced SAR-slick scientists were used as "correct" slick type.

The results revealed that all oil spills were correctly classified. The two look-alikes classified as oil were both caused by other pollution from oil platforms. The expected problem with natural films being classified as oil was not reflected in the results. The reason is probably that "doubt" cases were not included in the test data set. Only verified slicks and slicks previously classified as highly likely to be caused by natural films, were included.

Authors

Heidi A. Espedal

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

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Ola M. Johannessen
Director

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Copies can be obtained from
Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Edv. Griegsv. 3a
N-5037 Solheimsviken-Bergen, Norway
Tel: +47 55 29 72 88, Fax: +47 55 20 00 50
E-mail: Ola.Johannessen@nrsc.no

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Abstract

Spaceborne Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) is currently being used on an operational basis for near real-time oil pollution monitoring in Norwegian waters. However, the SAR backscatter values from oil spills are not unique. Several look-alikes may also dampen out the capillary and short gravity waves which are sensed by the SAR, and cause dark areas (slicks) in the imagery. At present, the oil spill surveillance performed at Tromsø Satellite Station is only based on an operators' experience in slick classification. This report describes a supervised algorithm developed to supply a standard procedure, including tools to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process.

1 Introduction

Surveillance is one important element in the management of coastal waters, both for ensuring compliance to pollution regulations and for making decisions on whether or not to start major cleanup operations against, for example, oil spills. North Sea countries have for more than a decade been flying side-looking airborne radar (SLAR) in order to detect oil spills. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images from satellites can be used for the same purpose. Among the advantages of satellite SAR is the possibility to cover large and remote areas, and its cost effectiveness compared to airborne surveillance. However, the major disadvantage is a number of oil spill look-alikes found in the SAR (and SLAR) imagery. Several other phenomena may dampen out the capillary and short gravity waves sensed by the SAR and cause dark areas, generally called slicks, to appear in the imagery. These include other man-made pollutants (produced water, drilling mud and drain water), current wakes and ship wakes, oil seepage, natural films, grease ice, threshold wind, wind sheltering by land, rain cells, internal waves and current convergence zones [Espedal, 1998].

The oil spill look-alikes in the SAR imagery have made it necessary to develop algorithms to ensure that the risk of false alarms are minimized, or preferably, eliminated. In addition to the supervised slick discrimination algorithm described in this work (preliminary version first published in [Hovland-Espedal *et al.*, 1994a; 1994b]), an extensive literature search has located only two other algorithms being developed. The algorithm described by Weisteen *et al.* [1993] detects slicks and provides automatic extraction of slick features. Those classified as possible oil spills should thereafter be subjected to human inspection. However, no attempt was made to develop methods for this human inspection, or contextual analysis. The other algorithm described in [Sloggett and Jory, 1994; 1995] is developed to detect, analyze and supply a conclusion of whether a slick in a SAR image is caused by an oil spill. Unfortunately, according to Sloggett [*pers.comm.*, 1998] no updated papers with details or validation of this algorithm has been published. Moreover, experience has shown that the capability of the human eye and brain in detecting and discriminating between slicks is far beyond the reach of today's computers [Wahl *et al.*, 1996]. As long as coverage is

limited by interest in high priority regions, manual interpretation is feasible. However, good tools within a frame of a supervised slick discrimination algorithm, can supply a standard procedure to be followed which will be very useful in satellite SAR slick discrimination. The main objective of the work reported here, was therefore to develop a standard procedure including tools, to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process with focus on oil spills. This may in turn improve our understanding of SAR imaging of slicks, and eventually help to develop satellite SAR as tool in oil spill surveillance.

The flow chart in Fig. 1 outlines the major steps in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm. The algorithm is written using Interactive Data Language (IDL), a software program for interactive analysis and visualization of scientific and engineering data [Research Systems Inc., 1992b; 1992a]. It was chosen because of its numerous mathematical analysis and graphical display techniques. The algorithm has been tested on 124 slicks in ERS SAR imagery. However, to describe the details of the method and how it was developed, one single slick has been chosen as an example used throughout this report.

First a short description of the initial processing is given in section 2, while the details are left to Appendix A. The direct analysis (Box 1, Fig. 1) includes all information that can be drawn from the slick itself, e.g. shape, size, damping, texture and gradients. This is described in section 3. The contextual analysis (Box 2, Fig. 1), described in section 4, includes additional information that may be relevant in the slick discrimination process. Wind, current, slick age determination, rain, temperature/season, bathymetry and location of possible pollution sources, all give important input here. Section 5 briefly describes an oil drift model and the Environmental Research Institute of Michigan (ERIM) SAR Ocean Model (Box 3 and 4, Fig. 1). These models have been tested for usefulness in a slick discrimination process. In section 6 conclusions are drawn based on the combined information from the slick discrimination process, while section 7 gives some results of a comparison between slick properties for oil spills and natural films. No one-to-one relationship between slick properties and slick type was found. However, some trends can be seen. Finally, section 8 provides the results from testing the supervised slick discrimination algorithm on 124 ERS SAR slicks. These included 34 confirmed oil spills, 5 cases confirmed to be other pollution, and 5 confirmed natural films.

2 Initial processing of the SAR images

The SAR data used in this work were mainly ERS low resolution images (LRI) obtained from Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS). The supervised slick discrimination algorithm was therefore developed with focus on these data. The initial processing of the images includes range normalization, linear scaling from 16 to 8 bit pixels, resampling to square 100m pixels and absolute calibration. Powerloss due to Analogue to Digital Convertor (ADC) saturation has not yet been implemented in the LRI processing. This will effect

Analysis of slicks in SAR imagery

Figure 1: A flow chart indicating the main steps in the supervised SAR oil slick discrimination algorithm.

backscatter values especially in near range in rough weather. Special care was therefore taken when encountering slicks in such cases during algorithm development. Since very little literature exist on correction and calibration of TSS SAR imagery, a comparison was made between SAR scenes obtained both as TSS low resolution imagery (LRI) and as ESA Precision Imagery (PRI). The latter is corrected and calibrated according to [Laur *et al.*, 1996], including ADC corrections. The results indicated that the differences in backscatter remained less than 1.5dB, and were mainly caused by the lack of ADC correction in TSS LRI images, and the different methods of calculating the calibration constant K. Methods for implementing ADC corrections for LRI imagery are currently being investigated. The algorithm will also be extended to allow analysis of PRI imagery.

Details of the processing of LRI images and the comparison between TSS LRI and ESA PRI imagery, are described in Appendix A.

3 The direct analysis

When a SAR image has been through the initial processing, the first step in the discrimination process is the direct analysis (Box 1, Fig. 1). This encompass all the information that can be derived from the slick itself, i.e. shape, size, length, texture, damping and gradients. To illustrate the different steps of the supervised algorithm, an ERS-1 SAR image from 11 July 1994 is used as an example. The whole SAR scene (100 × 100 km) is first displayed with a pixel grid overlayed (Fig. 2). The image is then divided into subimages before each slick is analyzed separately. A description of what is seen in the image, will therefore emerge from the discussion below.

Several edge detection filters have been tested for implementation in the slick algorithm. The usefulness of such operators is twofold;

1. as an automatic screening of SAR imagery, removing all ocean images without any specific edges, e.g. slick features. This will reduce the amount of SAR data that need to be visually investigated.
2. aid in inspection when listing the slicks (if any) to be studied further using the supervised discrimination algorithm.

For these purposes, fairly simple operators can be sufficient. I therefore selected the basic Sobel and Robert gradient filters for implementation in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm. For an image $f(x,y)$, the gradient at a pixel location (x,y) is [Gonzalez and Woods, 1992]

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f &= \left[\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \\ &\approx \left| \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \right| + \left| \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \right| \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: A descending ERS-1 SAR image from 11/7-94 (10:59UTC) with a grid overlaid indicating pixel number along the x- and y-axis.

Where terms of the type $\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}\right)$ have been neglected. The gradient operators approximates the gradient at a pixel location (x,y) . The Sobel function is given by

$$\nabla f \approx |(z_7 + 2z_8 + z_9) - (z_1 + 2z_2 + z_3)| + |(z_3 + 2z_6 + z_9) - (z_1 + 2z_4 + z_7)| \quad (2)$$

for the center pixel z_5 in a region described by

$$\begin{bmatrix} z_1 & z_2 & z_3 \\ z_4 & z_5 & z_6 \\ z_7 & z_8 & z_9 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The Sobel filter thus approximates the gradients as differences in pixel values between the first and third row, and the first and third column. It therefore gives strongest response for edges in the x and y directions. A cross gradient operator called the Robert filter was implemented for improved detectability of angled edges.

$$\nabla f \approx |z_5 - z_9| + |z_6 - z_8| \quad (4)$$

Some time was also spent investigating the Laplacian operator, i.e. the filter was tested on selected SAR imagery. The Laplacian operator gives the second derivative of the image $f(x,y)$. This operator also detects edges, but is very sensitive to noise and is also unable to detect edge direction [Gonzalez and Woods, 1992]. It was therefore not implemented in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm.

Fig. 3 shows the results when using the Sobel and Roberts edge detectors on a subimage of Fig. 2. The subimage contained 5 slicks that should be analyzed in more detail. However, slick A was chosen to demonstrate the following analysis.

Figure 3: Result when using (a) the Sobel filter, and (b) the Robert filter for a 200×200 pixels subimage of Fig. 2.

From the grid in Fig. 2 a subimage, usually 200×200 pixels, covering slick A is chosen. The subimage covering slick A is displayed together with a contour plot (for shape analysis), and a profile crossing the slick in azimuth and range directions (Fig. 4). The different parameters are then extracted from the slick;

- **Source;** if the source of the slick is detected (bright spot connected to or near the slick, see Fig. 4a), this is registered; yes/no, connected/near.
- **Shape;** the contour plot in Fig. 4b displays pixels with values less than a specified value, k , as black, and the rest as white. The threshold value, k , is selected so that the interclass variance between dark and bright regions in the subimage is maximized. According to [Reddi *et al.*, 1984; Lindberg and Wahl, 1995], the criterion for selecting

Figure 4: The 200 x 200 pixels subscene covering slick A, a contour plot, and a profile crossing the slick in azimuth and range directions.

k becomes

$$m_b + m_d = 2k \quad (5)$$

where m_b is the mean of the bright pixels and m_d is the mean of the dark pixels, both given as V_8 the digital 8-bit values in the image (proportional to the square root of the intensity, see Appendix A). Together with the Sobel and Robert edge enhancement filters, this provides the basis for determining the shape of the slick. The shape categories used in this study have been determined based on the work performed in [Espedal, 1998; Espedal and Wahl, 1998; Espedal *et al.*, 1998]. These categories and the typical corresponding phenomena are given in Table 1 and illustrated in Fig. 5.

Table 1: Shape categories.

No.	Characteristics	Phenomena
1	Long & thin & curving	Oil spills/Other pollutants/Natural film
2	Long & thin & straight	Young spills/Ship wakes/Current wakes
3	Wide/rounded	Grease ice/Oil spills/Natural film
4	Droplets	Natural oil seepage
5	Dense	Natural oil seepage
6	Large & homogeneous	Low wind
7	Large & fractal	Natural films
8	Dense dark centers surrounded by bright cells	Rain cells
9	Very narrow & curving	Shear zones/Natural film
10	Series of parallel dark (bright) bands	Internal waves

- **Size/Dimensions;** The number of pixels in slick A displayed as black in the contour plot (Fig. 4b) is given. This provides a measure of slick area. An estimate of slick dimensions is also given (length and width).
- **Texture** (see e.g. [MacGrew and Monroe, 1993]); To investigate the texture of the slicks, a statistical approach using moments of the grey-level histograms was implemented. In addition to the mean value of the slick, the standard deviation, the range (maximum and minimum), skewness and kurtosis were calculated. The standard deviation is given by

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(V_{8,i} - \bar{V}_8)^2}{n - 1}} \quad (6)$$

where V_8 is the different 8 bit pixel values, and $\bar{V}_8$ is the mean of the slick. The sum is over all n pixels in the slick. The quantity $\sum(V_{8,i} - \bar{V}_8)^2$ is the second moment of the grey-level distribution. Standard deviation describes the variability (deviation from

(a) Long & thin & curving

(b) Long & thin & straight

(c) Wide/rounded

(d) Droplets

(e) Dense

(f) Large & homogeneous

(g) Large and fractal

(h) Dense dark surrounded by bright cells

(i) I. Very narrow & curving, II. Parallel bands

Figure 5: Shape categories (all images are 25 × 25km).

the mean) in the distribution. Skewness involves the third moment of the grey-level distribution;

$$Skewness = \frac{\sum(V_{8,i} - \bar{V}_8)^3}{ns^3} \quad (7)$$

This gives a measure of the symmetry in the distribution (or histogram), i.e. if the values are evenly or unevenly distributed to either side of the mean. If the skewness is zero, the distribution is symmetric. If it is negative (positive), the histogram has a tail to the left (right). The kurtosis measures the flatness or peakedness of a data set, and involves the fourth moment of the grey-level distribution;

$$Kurtosis = \frac{\sum(V_{8,i} - \bar{V}_8)^4}{ns^4} - 3 \quad (8)$$

A normal distribution has zero kurtosis. A peaked distribution (with a large portion of all values clustered in one part of the distribution) has positive kurtosis, while a flat distribution (with values spread more evenly over many different parts of the distribution) has negative kurtosis.

Both skewness and kurtosis are standardized by using the standard deviation in the denominators.

- **Damping;** Backscatter damping caused by a slick is given by extracting the mean backscatter value of the slick and a nearby homogeneous non-slicked region (usually a polygon of 5×5 km size), and calculating the difference;

$$Damping [dB] = \sigma_{non-slick} [dB] - \sigma_{slicked} [dB] \quad (9)$$

- **Gradients;** The gradient should reflect how smooth the edges of a slick are, i.e. how the backscatter changes over a given distance. The profiles crossing slick A in Fig. 4 are averaged over 5 lines (or columns). From such plots the gradients may be calculated. The gradient at location $i + 1$ is given by

$$z_{i+2} - z_i [dB/200m] \quad (10)$$

where z_i is the backscatter value at location i . The quantity $z_{i+2} - z_i$ is plotted for slick A in Fig. 6. The maximum values of $z_{i+2} - z_i$ when going into and out of the slick, are averaged and used for gradient calculation. The gradient for slick A was thus found to be 1.4 dB/100m. Other ways of describing slick edges are currently being investigated. One method could be to use the backscatter profile through a slick, to estimate the “width” of the slick edge. This can be done by measuring the distance between the last pixel (near the slick) containing the average non-slicked backscatter value and the first pixel containing the average slick backscatter value. The gradient could then be described as

$$\frac{Damping [dB]}{Slick\ edge\ width [m]} \quad (11)$$

where damping is given by equation 9. Expression 11 should be normalized to $\Delta\text{dB}/100\text{m}$ to simplify comparison.

The different values extracted for slick A in Fig. 4 are given in Table 2. A bright point is connected to the slick, and the slick is therefore emitted from this source. Bright points connected to or near slicks are thus strong spill indicators. The slick shape is long & thin & curving, i.e. classified as belonging to category 1. This shape category is dominated by slicks caused by oil, other pollution or natural film (Table 1). Slick A is approximately 6.7km long and 1.5 km wide, with a total of 38 pixels below the threshold value k . The maximum and minimum pixel values in the slick are both approximately 2 standard deviations from the mean, i.e. a little for the maximum pixel value. This results in a slightly positive skewness. The negative kurtosis indicates a flat distribution of the V_8 values within the slick, i.e. the slick backscatter values are dispersed over different values. The damping caused by slick A is 3.7dB, while the gradient is 1.4dB/100m. However, as previous studies have shown, see e.g. [Weisteen *et al.*, 1993; Wahl *et al.*, 1994; Espedal, 1998], none of the properties extracted directly from a slick in a SAR image give a one-to-one correlation with a slick phenomena. To support a conclusion on slick type, a contextual analysis is therefore necessary.

Table 2: Features extracted from the slick A in Fig. 4.

Slick A		
Source	yes	connected
Shape	category 1	long & thin & curving
Size:	(nbre of pixels)	38*
Dimensions:	(length $\times$ width)	8km / 2km
Mean (slick)	$(V_8 \rightarrow \sigma^0)$	40.37 $\rightarrow$ -15.3dB
Mean (non-slick)	$(V_8 \rightarrow \sigma^0)$	61.33 $\rightarrow$ -11.6dB
Threshold value (k)	$(V_8 \rightarrow \sigma^0)$	50.85 $\rightarrow$ -13.3dB
Texture:	Std. dev. (V_8)	8.36796
	max / min ($V_8 \rightarrow \sigma^0$)	56 / 27 $\rightarrow$ -12.4dB / -18.8dB
	Skewness	0.067571
	Kurtosis	-1.37264
Damp.		3.7dB
Gradient:		1.4dB/100m

$\sigma^0 = 20\log_{10} V_8 - 47.4$ [dB], V_8 is the pixel value.

*Pixel size is $100 \times 100\text{m}$.

Figure 6: The quantity $z_{i+2} - z_i$ plotted when crossing slick A in the range direction.

4 The contextual analysis

The contextual analysis (Box 2, Fig. 1) is based on information from the region surrounding the slick. This includes local winds, currents, rain, temperature/season, bathymetry and location of possible pollution sources. The first step in the contextual analysis of the supervised slick discrimination algorithm is to produce a map indicating the location and coverage of the SAR scene. Fig. 7 illustrates this for the SAR image from 11 July 1994. The figure also outlines the main study area of this work. On top of this coverage map, several parameters may be included. These are described below.

Figure 7: The main study area of this work. The box indicates the coverage of the SAR scene from 11/7-94 (Fig. 4).

4.1 Wind and currents

A SAR image depicts the backscatter from the ocean surface at a given point in time by sensing capillary and short gravity waves (approximately 7cm long for the ERS-1 C-band SAR). Instantaneous wind (wind speed and direction nearest in time and space to the slick) is therefore very important when looking for oil spills in SAR imagery. A slick that remains connected at wind speeds above 7-8m/s is highly likely to contain oil, since all types of natural slicks will disperse at such strong winds [Scott, 1986; Espedal and Wahl, 1998] or their damping effect will disappear in the noise of wind generated waves [Demin *et al.*, 1985]. Furthermore, the temporal evolution of the wind (the wind history) during the day(s) before SAR imaging, may also contribute in the interpretation process. The shape of bent or angular slicks can be matched against wind history to estimate slick age. A spill

from a fixed source is assumed to move with 3% of the wind speed, and 15° to the right of the wind direction on the northern hemisphere [Bern, 1993; ASCE-Task-Committee, 1996].

This study was based on wind information only, since current data was not available. The result of including a background current, would be a slick drift vector obtained by vector-adding the current to the wind effect.

4.1.1 Instantaneous wind based on measurements

Digital hindcast wind data for the study region defined in Fig. 7, can be obtained from the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI). These are model results based on a large number of continuously updated in situ observations. The spatial grid is 75km, while the temporal resolution is 6hours. The wind data closest in time to SAR imaging on 11 July 1994 (10:59UTC), was at 12:00UTC (Fig. 8). According to model results, the wind speed was 5m/s from the south, which are ideal conditions for SAR slick detection, including oil spills and natural films. Today, weather forecast models at DNMI are run on test case basis with a spatial resolution of 10km and temporal resolution of 3hours. Unfortunately, these data have so far not been commercially available.

Figure 8: The hindcast wind data from 11 July 1994, 12:00UTC.

The digital hindcast data are therefore often supplemented with weather maps. Such maps, containing in situ observations of wind, are available with a temporal resolution

of 3hours. In some cases, the wind vectors obtained from these weather maps are closer (temporally and/or spatially) to a slick than the hindcast results. For the example shown here, the weather maps (9UTC and 12UTC) indicated wind speeds of 2-3m/s from the south/southwest approximately 20km from slick A. For such low winds the short gravity and capillary waves observed by the SAR, are practically not generated. This results in large dark areas in the SAR imagery, such as seen in the bottom right part of Fig. 2. However, the local wind near slick A must have been above the threshold wind, since this region is not black in the SAR image.

To obtain an even better spatial resolution of the wind vectors at the time of imaging, wind can be retrieved directly from the SAR image. Several empirical models are used today in SAR wind determination, e.g. the CMOD4 [Shuchman *et al.*, 1993, Vachon and Dobson, 1996; Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998] and the SAR wind algorithm (SWA) [Vachon *et al.*, 1994; Chapron *et al.*, 1995; Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998]. So far, only the CMOD4 has been used in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm. Furure work will therefore include testing of the SAR wind algorithm (SWA).

4.1.2 Instantaneous wind using CMOD4

When imaging the sea surface, the returned signal to the SAR depends on the wind speed and direction. The CMOD4 model was originally developed for wind retrieval from the ERS-1 C-band scatterometer [Stoffelen and Anderson, 1994]. However, CMOD4 has also been used on ERS SAR imagery with satisfactory results [Shuchman *et al.*, 1993, Vachon and Dobson, 1996; Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998]. The CMOD4 is written as

$$\sigma_0 = b_0[1 + b_1 \cos(\phi) + b_2 \cos(2\phi)] \quad (12)$$

where b_0 , b_1 and b_2 , depend on the local radar incidence angle and wind speed. The quantity ϕ is the radar look angle relative to the wind direction ($\phi=0$ when the wind is blowing towards the radar). This means that to obtain estimates of wind speed, wind direction has to be known or vica versa. When using the CMOD4 to obtain wind direction based on backscatter and wind speed, Eq. 12 has four solutions, i.e. two pairs, each with a 180° ambiguity (exept near upwind/downwind where there is only one solution pair). The estimated accuracy for CMOD4 applied to scatterometer data, is ± 2 m/s in wind speed and $\pm 20^\circ$ in relative wind direction. In Fig. 9 the solution of Eq. 12 is shown for an incidence angle of 23°.

The problem when using the CMOD4 for wind speed estimation, is that the wind direction has to be known. In some cases, wind direction can be derived directly from the SAR imagery (offshore winds causing land sheltering, or presence of windrows [Johannessen *et al.*, 1995]), otherwise the wind direction is estimated using weather maps. For the case from 11 July 1994, the wind direction was derived from weather maps indicating winds

Figure 9: The CMOD4 for a 23° incidence angle. The figure demonstrates clearly that a given backscatter and wind speed gives 4 possible wind directions when using CMOD4. (Plot by © E. Korsbakken).

Figure 10: Results when using CMOD4 for slick A in Fig. 4.

from south ($Wdir=180^\circ$), The relative direction, ϕ , can be written

$$\phi = Wdir - 81.5^\circ \quad (13)$$

for a right looking radar and a spacecraft inclination of 98.5° . Using CMOD4 for a backscatter of -11.6dB (outside slick A in Fig. 4) and $\phi=98.5$, then gave a wind speed of $2\text{m/s}\pm 2\text{m/s}$ (Fig. 10). As previously mentioned, the wind near slick A must be $\geq 2\text{-}3\text{m/s}$, since this area is not black in the SAR image. Remembering the hindcast wind of 5m/s and in situ measurement of $2\text{-}3\text{m/s}$ from the weather maps, we therefore conclude that the local wind, near the slick at the time of imaging, is $3\text{-}4\text{m/s}$.

The CMOD4 data obtained in this work are results from a fortran program developed based on [Lecomte, 1993]. An improved version of CMOD4 has now been written using IDL [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998], and will be implemented in the slick discrimination algorithm in the near future. The IDL routine is based on ESA Precision Images (PRI), and it will need modification before being used on SAR imagery from Tromsø Satellite Station. Moreover, ESA routines for providing relevant calibrations parameters must be implemented at Tromsø Satellite Station.

4.1.3 Age estimation using wind history

Wind history may be very useful in cases of abrupt changes in slick direction. Together with slick length, knowledge of wind history can be used to estimate a minimum and/or maximum age of tail slicks (i.e. narrow, linear slicks). If oil is spilled from a fixed point source at North Sea latitudes, it is assumed to move with 3% of the wind speed, 15° to the right of the wind direction [Bern, 1993; ASCE-Task-Committe, 1996], provided that no (strong) surface current is present and that no other factors have a great influence on the spread pattern. If wind is the only major factor influencing the spill shape, a linear relationship between the age of a slick, its length and the wind speed can be found. A continuous release of oil from the source is then assumed. Such a linear model between wind speed and slick length can only be used as a guideline since the assumption that wind is the most dominant (or only) factor influencing an oil spill, is not always valid. Other important factors can be currents, viscosity and amount of slick material. These parameters are, however, generally not known when a slick is discovered in a SAR image. Accurate computations of the slick age also require detailed knowledge of the wind (and surface current) fields, preferably with a temporal resolution of 1-3hours. In an operational context, it is usually sufficient to use only the *changes* in wind (and surface current) direction as an indication of how the slick has evolved over time, and thus roughly estimate slick age [Espedal and Wahl, 1998].

The procedure for estimating the age of slick A in Fig. 4, follows the flow charts in Figs. 11-12. The numbers below correspond to those given in Fig. 11;

1. A bright spot indicating the slick source (platform or ship), can be seen in the image. Move to step 2.
2. The spot corresponds with a platform location, i.e. a fixed source. Move to step 4.
4. Perform wind history and slick shape matching using the observed source as a starting point.

The numbers below match those given in Fig. 12.

1. The wind history necessary to generate the slick configuration seen in the SAR image is drawn, while keeping in mind that the part closest to the slick has been generated most recently. The result is shown in Fig. 13.

2. Compare with measured (or modeled) wind history (Fig. 13), and look for similar changes in wind direction. The wind data was measured at point A seen in the location map. At this location the wind at 9:00UTC (11-7-94) matched that of part c and the wind at 6:00UTC on 10-7-94 matched part b. The oldest part of the slick (part a) matched the wind at 21UTC on 9-7-94, i.e. 1 1/2 day (38hours) before imaging. A more detailed analysis of slick length vs. wind speed (step 3, Fig. 12) is not necessary, since a slick having survived more than 38hours, even when the wind remained 7.5–10m/s for a long period, is a strong indicator of a spill containing oil.

This method of wind history vs. slick shape matching developed by Espedal and Wahl [1998] is in practical use at Tromsø Satellite Station in their operational satellite SAR oil spill detection service.

4.2 Rain and temperature/season

Two oil spill look-alikes which generally are fairly easy to rule out in the contextual analysis, are rain cells and grease ice [Espedal, 1998; Espedal *et al.*, 1998]. Information on precipitation or location of high and low pressure systems, is of help when deciding whether or not a slick can be caused by a rain cell. An example of a rain cell is shown in Fig. 5h. Furthermore, based on knowledge of air (and sea) temperature or simply the season, grease ice can often be eliminated as a possible slick forming material.

Figure 11: Procedure for estimating slick age. The figure is taken from [Espedal and Wahl, 1998].

Figure 12: Procedure for wind history and slick configuration matching [Espedal and Wahl, 1998]. The slick direction should be 15° to the right of the wind direction. T1 is the time when the wind direction changed.

Figure 13: The wind history vs. slick shape analysis for slick A from Fig. 4. This subsene of the SAR image from 11-07-94 (10:59UTC) covers 25 × 25km. The location of both the (total) SAR scene and the wind measurements (A) are indicated on the map to the right. Under the map, the wind history necessary to generate the current slick shape, and the measured wind history are indicated (notice that the North direction is slightly different for the SAR image and the wind history box). T1 and T2 are the times when the wind direction changed.

4.3 Bathymetry

A tidal flow or current in shallow waters is modified when changes in water column height occur. The result is a flow pattern which mimics bottom topography. The short waves detected by the SAR are modified by such flow patterns, and bathymetry in shallow waters ($\leq 50\text{m}$, depending on currents) can thus be observed in SAR imagery [Wensink, 1997; Jenkins *et al.*, 1997]. A region of low backscatter (a slick) is usually found on the upstream side and a band of higher backscatter is seen on the downstream side of the bottom features (Fig. 14). These surface signatures have been speculated to be due to turbulence generated over the bottom topography, or by straining of surface ripples by horizontal tidal-velocity gradients occurring when tides flow over the shallow topography [Robinson, 1985].

Figure 14: Cartoon illustrating how sea bottom topography affect SAR backscatter.

The bathymetry of the North Sea (Fig. 7 and Fig. 15) is one of the most thoroughly mapped continental shelves in the world. This is due to both petroleum industry and governmental interest. In the southern part of the North Sea, near the coast of Belgium and the Netherlands, several reports exist on strong effects of bathymetry in SAR images [Hesselmans *et al.*, 1994; Wensink, 1997]. Following Kattegat into the Baltic Sea, the shallow water with strong depth gradients can give rise to flow patterns giving signatures in SAR imagery. A detailed map of the bathymetry in this region is give in Fig. 16.

In the Norwegian Sea (Fig. 7 and Fig. 15) there are less shallow waters, and bathymetry is therefore of minor importance in SAR image analysis here, except in coastal regions when tidal currents are strong.

Thus, the bathymetry is not an important factor when analyzing slick A in the SAR image from 11/7-94 (Fig. 4), due to the fact that this region have no shallow waters. An example where bathymetry has to be considered is shown in Fig. 17. Several dark (slicks) and bright features can be seen in the SAR image. Here strong currents up to 0.5m/s are flowing northwards in a shallow water region where the depth is varying, but remains below 50m . This is ideal conditions for SAR detection of slicks caused by bathymetry.

Figure 15: Bathymetry of the study area.

Figure 16: Detailed bathymetry of the region from Kattegat to the Baltic Sea.

Figure 17: SAR image (10×10 km) from 3/8-95 of the Plaatgat site (Fig. 7), where bathymetry is an important factor when analyzing SAR imagery. The depth is less than 15m. ©RWS.

4.4 Locations of possible spill sources

The regions studied in this work, i.e. the Norwegian sea, the North Sea and the Baltic Sea, are areas with heavy ship traffic related to oil installations, refineries, oil terminals, fishing industry and other shipping industries. The extensive industry and ship traffic give high risk for both intentional and accidental oil pollution at sea. In a SAR oil spill detection system it is therefore necessary to include a database containing a list of name, cite type, company and coordinates of possible pollutions sources, so-called “hot-spots”. Such a data base has been developed in this work (see Appendix B). However, so far it mainly contains locations in the North Sea and the Norwegian Sea (Fig. 18). Lists of “hot-spots” in the Baltic exist, but corresponding exact coordinates have proven difficult to obtain. This work is ongoing, and the database is subject to continuous updating.

In the contextual analysis of a SAR image, the location of the image is displayed together with the locations of oil platforms and factories along the coast. The “hot-spots” are extracted from the above mentioned database. Still using slick A from 11/7-94 (Fig. 2 and Fig. 4) as an example, the map with possible spill sources overlayed are shown in Fig. 18. A zoomed version of this map is shown in Fig. 19. The names of the installations may also be written on the map. However, as is the case for the example presented here, when too many installations are close together the names will be unreadable (Figs. 20–21). A list of the names and coordinates of the possible spill sources in and near the SAR scene, can therefore also be written to a file or to the computer screen. This list can be compared

against the coordinates of the slick or slick source. The names of the platforms and factories can also be overlayed on the SAR image. This is shown for the SAR scene from 11/7-94 in Fig. 22. There are slicks behind several of the oil platforms. The source of slick A is the Statfjord B platform which, according to Appendix B, is a production platform. The slick could therefore be either oil or another man-made pollution (produced water, drilling mud or drain water) being released from the platform.

The total "hot-spot" database can be found in Appendix B.

Figure 18: Map showing SAR coverage and possible spill sources overlaid. Red; UK, green; Dutch, orange; Danish, blue; Norwegian installations.

Figure 19: Zooming in on SAR scene and hot-spots. Red; UK, blue; Norwegian installations.

Figure 20: Zooming in on SAR scene with names of hot-spots overlaid.

Figure 21: Zooming in on relevant hot-spots. The source of slick A (Fig.4) is the Statfjord B platform.

Figure 22: Hot-spots overlaid a subscene of the SAR image.

5 Models

If a slick in a SAR image has been through the direct and contextual analysis, and it has not been identified, modeling the behavior of spills and their typical SAR characteristics may help in the discrimination process. This modeling must be based on the relevant environmental conditions for the slick being studied. In this work two models have been tested; a numerical oil drift model [Furnes, 1994] and the ERIM SAR Ocean Model (EOM) [Tanis *et al.*, 1989a].

5.1 Oil drift model

To investigate the behavior of a possible oil spill under relevant weather conditions in more detail, a dispersion model, using a particle tracking random walk method was available for testing (Box 4, Fig. 1) [Furnes, 1994]. In this model, the spilled substance is modeled by an assemblage of discrete particles, which can be subjected to advection, diffusion and various decay processes. The advection is simulated by a translation of the individual particles in the local fluid velocity field, while the diffusion is simulated by a random walk technique, which displaces each particle a distance derived from the variance of a given distribution function.

The model was tested on a few slick cases, e.g. the result for a slick from the Murchison platform is shown in Figs. 23-24 [Espedal and Wahl, 1998]. After a continuous spill during three days, the model reproduces fairly well the slick seen in Fig. 23. However, the modeled slick is not as bent as the SAR imaged slick, indicating that the spill may have started more than three days before SAR imaging. A slick having survived that long on the ocean surface is very likely to contain oil.

Unfortunately this model is not commercially available. For implementation in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm, other available models are currently being investigated, e.g. the OILWATCH model [Applied-Science-Associates-Inc., 1998]. This model has several user options, e.g. spill scenarios can be specified (including oil type and wind time series), current fields can be generated and spill trajectories displayed. Another option is to develop a new oil drift model to be implemented in the slick discrimination algorithm.

5.2 The ERIM SAR Ocean Model (EOM)

In order to interpret SAR images of slicks, it is useful to have available models which can give quantitative estimates of relevant geophysical parameters, based on SAR data, other measurements and background information (if available). Several numerical models have the possibility to implement the effect of surface slicks on the radar backscatter. However, EOM was the only one available that already includes slick effects. It was therefore chosen for testing the usefulness of SAR modeling in the supervised slick discrimination algorithm (Box 3, Fig. 1).

Figure 23: A SAR image from 30 October 1994 showing a long & thin & curving slick connected to the Murchison platform. This subscene covers 50×50 km.

Figure 24: Simulation result for the movement of a possible spill from the Murchison platform. Wind, current and wave height measurements from Gullfaks C and a discharge rate of 1000 tons of diesel pr. hour, was used as input to the model. The discharge rate is believed to be overestimated in this simulation.

EOM is an integrated hydrodynamic and electromagnetic model that provides a full-spectrum solution to the wave action equation, using a two-scale composite radar backscatter model [Tanis *et al.*, 1989a; Tanis *et al.*, 1989b]. The wave spectral density is computed with reference to an equilibrium spectrum which is dependent on wind speed and direction [Lyzenga and Bennett, 1988], using a quadratic wave growth-relaxation source term based on [Huges, 1978] and [Plant, 1982]. The effect of surfactants on short gravity and capillary waves is included by adding an extra damping term to the right-hand side of the wave action equation, using the formulation of [Levich, 1962; Dorrestein, 1951]. It uses an empirical model for the surface elasticity as a function of film pressure. The hydrodynamic model output is the two-dimensional wave spectrum at each spatial grid point. The electromagnetic scattering from the ocean surface uses a physical optics assumption for large scale structure, and approximates the long-wave tilt effects on the small-scale Bragg scattering. SAR motion effects (including velocity bunching) and speckle, are also taken into account. Fig. 25 shows the structure of the EOM program.

The key parameter in EOM slick modeling is the surfactant pressure, which can range from 0 dynes/cm (no film) to 100 dynes/cm. The typical values for monomolecular surfactants is 0.2–40 dynes/cm [Jarvis, 1967; Jarvis *et al.*, 1967; Persen, 1981; Snik *et al.*, 1983]. However, the formulations are relevant only for thin films, i.e. thick oil spills cannot at present be modeled by EOM. Therefore, the model can only be used to estimate general trends in dB-values given typical surfactant values, under the relevant environmental conditions. This may however, in certain cases, give important additional information in a slick discrimination process.

For slick A in the descending SAR image from 11 June 1994 (Fig. 4a), the corresponding wind was estimated to be 3–4 m/s from the south. The backscatter was -11.9 dB outside the slick, and -16.6 dB inside the slick. This corresponds to a damping of 4.7 dB. In Fig. 26 the backscatter is plotted as a function of surfactant pressure, using EOM modeling results. The plot is obtained using the following input environmental and radar parameters;

Wind speed	3.5 m/s
Wind direction	285° (relative to the radar range direction, anticlockwise)
Current	0
Salinity	35‰
Surfactant pressure	0–50 dynes/cm
Temperature	15°
Radar freq.	5.3 GHz
Incidence angle	23.5°
Polarization	VV
Height of sensor	782 km
Velocity of sensor	7490 m/s
Wave spectrum	Lyzenga [Lyzenga and Bennett, 1988; Tanis <i>et al.</i> , 1989a]
Wind source function	Plant [1982]

Figure 25: The structure of the EOM program

Figure 26: Backscatter as a function of surfactant pressure. Wind speed is 3.5m/s, and wind direction is 278° (relative to the radar range direction, anticlockwise).

When comparing the backscatter values obtained from the SAR image with the plot in Fig. 26, a surfactant pressure of 0.7dynes/cm corresponds with the 4.7dB damping (compared to a slick free, 0dynes/cm, region). The backscatter observations and model results therefore indicate that some kind of surfactant film is present, but that it is not possible to determine its composition purely from the satellite radar observations. However, the model may be very useful as a basis for e.g. indicating which wind conditions (speed and direction) are optimal for slick detection, and which are less favorable.

For a predetermined surfactant pressure and different wind speeds, the damping caused by the surfactant can e.g. be investigated for different wind directions. This will give an indication of which wind directions and wind speeds that are best for slick detection. EOM was therefore run for two surfactant pressure values, 3dynes/cm and 40dynes/cm. Figs. 27-28 indicate that the higher surfactant pressure gives more damping, as expected. Moreover, the general trends are the same in both figures, e.g. winds from north or south (360° or 180°) give the strongest damping, while winds from east or west (90° or 270°) gave weakest damping (maximum 2dB difference in damping).

Figure 27: Results for surfactant pressure $P_0=3$ dynes/cm with different wind directions.

Figure 28: Results for surfactant pressure $P_0=40$ dynes/cm with different wind directions.

6 Drawing conclusions from the combined information for slick A

Based on the direct and contextual analysis and model results (if available), a conclusion is found. Slick A from Fig. 4 displayed shape, size, texture, damping and gradients previously found for oil spills, other pollutants or natural films. Natural film was discarded as an explanation due to the fact that the slick was connected to a source, i.e. the Statfjord B platform. To support the conclusion of slick A containing oil, the age of the slick was estimated using the local wind history. The slick shape corresponded with changes in wind direction occurring more than 1 1/2 day before SAR imaging. The fact that the slick has survived for this long, even when the wind was measured to be $\geq 7.5\text{m/s}$ for a long period, is a strong oil spill indicator. The other possible pollution spills from the platform (produced water, drilling mud and drain water), would all have disappeared from the surface [Espedal and Wahl, 1998]. Slick A is therefore classified as a spill containing oil.

7 Comparison of slick properties for oil spills and natural films

Even though all the phenomena that create dark slicks in the SAR imagery are potential oil spill look-alikes, it does not automatically follow that they are difficult to distinguish from oil slicks. Most of the look-alikes have very characteristic shapes and configurations, or depend on weather conditions [Espedal, 1998; Espedal and Wahl, 1998]. Of all the oil spill look-alikes, natural film proved to represent the largest problem for the oil spill discrimination algorithm. Therefore, several parameters for natural films and confirmed oil spills have been investigated and compared.

Figs. 29-30 show the backscatter damping in ERS SAR imagery vs. wind speed, caused by oil spills and natural films respectively. The results indicate that even though natural films and oil spills display similar damping at low wind speeds, natural film damping seems to fall off more quickly as wind speed increases. For natural films, the drop in backscatter varied between 2dB and 11dB, while for oil spills the damping varied between 1dB and 16dB (the smallest damping corresponded to a wind speed of approximately 17.5m/s). The wide range of damping values was probably due to varying slick composition and thickness.

To look at the texture differences for natural films and oil spills, a scatter plot of skewness vs. kurtosis was generated (Fig. 31). The results indicate that oil slicks display a slightly more positive value of the kurtosis. This means that generally the distribution of backscatter values for oil spills are more peaked. For natural film slicks the backscatter is more evenly dispersed over many different values. However, some slicks that display extremely high peakedness (kurtosis) also have the highest skewness. A few atypical backscatter

Figure 29: Plot of backscatter damping vs. wind speed, based on confirmed oil spills from 34 ERS-1/2 SAR scenes. The backscatter damping values are averaged at each wind speed, and the error bars indicate one standard deviation.

Figure 30: Plot of backscatter damping vs. wind speed, based on natural films from 71 ERS-1/2 SAR scenes [Espedal and Wahl, 1998]. The backscatter damping values are averaged at each wind speed, and the error bars indicate one standard deviation.

Figure 31: Plot of skewness vs. kurtosis for natural films and oil spills.

values will cause the whole distribution to become skewed, e.g. when a slick is fractal and may enclosed a non-slicked area. In these cases the mean backscatter value is usually not a good measure of the central tendency. Here the mode (the value occurring most frequently in the slick) may give a better representation of the slick backscatter.

In the operational oil spill detection service using satellite SAR imagery, performed at Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), oil slicks are expected to be more uniformly black and have sharper edges than look-alikes. These rules-of-thumb are based on experience with verified oil slicks in the SAR imagery. The slightly more positive value of the kurtosis for oil spills studied in this work, supports the the first criteria that oil slicks are more uniformly black. In Figs. 32-33 the gradient is plotted for oil spills and natural films. Fig. 33 includes gradient values for natural films at 10m/s. For such high wind speeds no natural film should have been detected [Demin *et al.*, 1985; Scott, 1986; Espedal, 1998]. In these cases the wind is believed to have been overestimated, since the slicks were found near land where sheltering effects may influence the local wind speed. However, the expected difference in edge sharpness is not found in the gradient plots of oil and natural film slicks (Figs. 32-33). This may be due to the way the gradient was calculated (see section 3). The estimate was only based on the maximum difference between neighboring pixels. Such a method may not capture the effect of diffuse edges properly. Future work should therefore include testing of different ways of describing slick edges, e.g. the wavelet method (see e.g. [Johannessen *et al.*, 1996] and references therein). One way may be to estimate the distance between the last pixel (near the slick) containing the average non-slicked backscatter value and the

first pixel containing the average slick backscatter value.

8 Results from slick analysis of 124 slicks in SAR imagery

The slick discrimination procedures were tested using SAR imagery with 34 confirmed oil slicks and 5 confirmed natural films [Espedal, 1998]. In addition, imagery containing different look-alikes classified by Skøelv *et al.* [1993], Wahl *et al.* [1994] and also some images analyzed at TSS were used. The results are indicated in Table 3.

Table 3: Matrix showing classification results.

Correct type↓	Classified as	
	Oil	Look-alike
Oil	34	0
Look-alike	2	88

In the look-alike group there were 3 cases of pollution (not oil) from factories, all correctly identified. The direct analysis indicated pollution as slick cause, but the wind history vs. slick shape matching did not identify oil as pollution source. However, the hot-spot data base identified the slick sources as factories (two images from a fish processing plant and one from an acid pitch disposal area). The slicks were therefore classified as fish oil and drainage from the acid pitch disposal area. This emphasises the importance of contextual information, i.e. based on the properties derived directly from the slicks in the SAR images, these could have been caused by oil spills. Continuous updating of the hot-spot data base is therefore very important and necessary for the supervised slick discrimination algorithm.

The two look-alikes classified as oil were actually other pollution from platforms. One of those are shown in (Fig. 34). The slick was connected to a platform at the Heidrun oil field (9 October 1993). The spill has been confirmed to contain 274m³ drilling fluid released nearly 24hours before SAR imaging. This indicates one of the problems when discriminating oil slicks from other pollutions spilled from oil installations or ships. Especially when wind history cannot aid in slick age estimation and verify that the slick has sustained rough weather conditions, it will be impossible to discriminate between pollution types using single frequency SAR.

As discussed in [Espedal *et al.*, 1996; Espedal *et al.*, 1998], we expected that some natural films would be classified as potential oil spills. This was not the case in the results given

Figure 32: Gradient values vs. wind speed for verified oil spills.

Figure 33: Gradient values vs. wind speed for natural films.

in Table 3. This is probably caused by the fact that among the 124 slicks used here, only natural films either verified or classified by other experienced slick investigators, are included. The “doubt” cases have therefore not been included. More verified natural films are necessary to test the supervised slick discrimination algorithm further. Future work should also include synergy studies, using SAR together with other satellite data such as visual ocean color and infrared.

Figure 34: Verified look-alike in ERS-1 SAR image from 9 October 1993.

9 Conclusions

The main objective of this work was

to develop a standard procedure including tools, to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process with focus on oil spills.

A supervised slick discrimination algorithm has been developed. It contains initial processing, slick detection and direct analysis, contextual analysis and model results. A conclusion is then based on information on typical properties of verified slicks and a hot-spot data base. The supervised algorithm performs best when contextual information is available. It supplies a procedure for slick discrimination which will help standardize operational oil spill detection using satellite SAR imagery.

Future work should include

- investigating new ways of describing slick edges. The currently used gradient parameter does not reflect the expected differences for oil spills and natural films.

- choosing or developing a new oil drift model to be implemented in the slick discrimination algorithm. This will help improve the slick age determination and give better indications of the weather conditions a slick has sustained.
- extending the ERIM SAR Ocean Model to include damping effects by thicker spills. This will allow for a better quantification of oil and natural film differences.
- updating the hot-spot data base to include the coordinates of the pollution sources in the Baltic Sea.
- more experiments to improve understanding of natural film formation processes, and to extend the number of verified slicks. This is important for both updating and testing the supervised slick discrimination algorithm.
- implementing ADC correction in the calibration of TSS LRI imagery.

Appendix A: Initial processing of the SAR images

This appendix describes the processing performed on the SAR images analyzed by the supervised slick discrimination algorithm. Data for this work was mainly obtained in the form of TSS low resolution ERS SAR imagery. Therefore, the processing method focused on these data. For PRI images from ESA, a processing program written by E. Korsbakken [*pers.comm.*] is available. When implementing this program, the supervised slick discrimination algorithm will be able to handle both TSS and ESA SAR images.

When Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS) receives data from the ERS SAR sensor, the processing includes;

- Conversion of instrument signal to digital integer numbers
- internal calibration to ensure instrument stability
- averaging from $20 \times 16\text{m}$ to $100 \times 80\text{m}$ (range $\times$ azimuth) pixel size

The resulting Low Resolution Image (LRI) file is only 2.5Mbytes, compared to the 63Mbytes of the original full resolution image (FRI) before averaging. One scene covers $100 \times 100\text{km}$. The format of the TSS LRI file is described in [TSS, 1991]. The image contains 1000 pixels in range and 1260 in azimuth. For each pixel, the backscatter is given by a 16 bit integer.

Correction and absolute calibration of the ERS SAR LRI

The backscattering coefficient σ^0 for a given pixel, can be computed from the TSS data as

$$\sigma^0 = \text{DN}^2 \times \text{rsl} \times \frac{1}{K} \times \frac{\sin \alpha}{\sin \alpha_{\text{ref}}} \times \frac{C}{C_{\text{ref}}} \times \frac{\text{ProductReplicaPower}}{\text{ReferenceReplicaPower}} \times \text{Powerloss} \quad (1)$$

where

- DN; digital number representing the value of a given pixel
- α ; local incidence angle (averaged over a pixel)
- α_{ref} ; reference incidence angle (23°)
- rsl; range-spreading loss compensation
- K; calibration constant
- $\frac{C}{C_{\text{ref}}}$; antenna gain pattern
- $\frac{\text{ProductReplicaPower}}{\text{ReferenceReplicaPower}}$; internal calibration
- Powerloss; saturation of ADC

The image geometry of the ERS-1/2 SAR is shown in Fig. 1. The powerloss is due to Analogue to Digital Convertor (ADC) saturation. It has not yet been implemented in the LRI processing at NERSC. However, the following processing is applied to all the LRI files in this study;

Figure 1: Imaging geometry of the ERS-1/2 SAR.

1. Internal calibration The replica pulse correction is part of the internal calibration system at TSS. Replica pulses are copies of the transmitted pulses. This calibration makes sure that the same sea state will give the same σ^0 in different images, i.e. accounts for instrument stability (this is already applied by TSS in LRI products).
2. Normalization in range To achieve a continuous greytone in range, an LRI image is corrected for;
 - Antenna gain pattern $\frac{C}{C_{ref}}$; C is the gain at the given pixel, and C_{ref} is the gain at 23° . The antenna gain expresses the extent to which the antenna of the radar concentrates the power from the transmitter, into a beam aimed at a target. The antenna does not radiate isotropically. Power is also lost by dissipation in the antenna itself. The antenna pattern is described by the curves in Fig. 2. These antenna patterns have been estimated using SAR imagery over the Brazilian rainforest [Laur *et al.*, 1993; 1996]. Extracting the mean range profile of 10 images of uniform rain forest, they assumed that the ratio $\sigma^0/\cos \alpha$ was constant for this rain forest (α is incidence angle).
 - Slant to ground conversion $\frac{\sin \alpha}{\sin \alpha_{ref}}$; α is the incidence angle at the given pixel, α_{ref} is the incidence angle at 23° . Accounts for the effect of slant-to-ground range conversion of the data. The difference is illustrated in Fig. 3.
 - Range-spreading loss compensation $rsl = \frac{R^3}{R_{ref}^3}$; R is the slant range at the given pixel, and R_{ref} is the slant range at 23° . Accounts for the fact that slant range R_s varies for different range pixels, i.e. the radar signal has a varying distance to travel depending on the range location (includes Earth curvature considera-

tions).

To make sure the strength of the return signal only relates to properties at the surface, and not the location in range, the above three compensations must be applied.

3. Linear scaling from 16 to 8 bit pixels In a typical LRI image delivered by TSS, all values are between 0–512. Since only 9 of the 16 bits are used, a conversion to 8 bit pixels will keep most of the information, while reducing the amount of data. The pixels from the ERS–1 SAR images are divided by 2.0, while pixels from ERS–2 SAR images are divided by 1.54;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ERS} - 1 ; V_8 &= \frac{\text{DN}}{2} \\ \text{ERS} - 2 ; V_8 &= \frac{\text{DN}}{1.54} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

All pixel values are then between 0–255 (after conversion to 8 bit pixels, all values larger than 255 will be set to 255). Using different divisors for ERS–1 and ERS–2 compensates for the difference in calibration constant K between the two instruments.

4. Resampling to square 100m pixels The resampling is done using nearest neighbor interpolation (no averaging or smoothing). The output image has 1024×1024 pixels.
5. Absolute calibration of σ^0 After the above corrections are made, σ^0 can be written as;

$$\sigma^0 = \text{DN}^2 \frac{1}{K} \quad (3)$$

In decibels the backscattering coefficient becomes;

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^0(\text{dB}) &= 10\log_{10}\text{DN}^2 - 10\log_{10}K \\ &= 20\log_{10}\text{DN} - K(\text{dB}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For ERS-1, K was found by comparing noise floor (-25.8dB) and homogeneous ice values during SIZEX92 [Malinas *et al.*, 1992], where the darkest areas (grease ice) had a pixel value DN=24. For ERS-2, K was found by comparing with near simultaneous images from ERS-1 during the tandem phase (data obtained during the COASTWATCH'95 experiment [Johannessen *et al.*, 1997]).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ERS} - 1 ; K &= 53.4\text{dB} \\ \text{ERS} - 2 ; K &= 51.1\text{dB} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Antenna pattern curves for ERS-1 and ERS-2.

Figure 3: Ground range and slant range display.

The following equations were therefore used in this study;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ERS} - 1 ; \sigma^0(\text{dB}) &= 20\log_{10}(2V_8) - 53.4 \\ &= 20\log_{10}V_8 - 47.4 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ERS} - 2 ; \sigma^0(\text{dB}) &= 20\log_{10}(1.54V_8) - 51.1 \\ &= 20\log_{10}V_8 - 47.4 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Equations 6 and 7 are the same.

To see the effect of range normalization (step 2 above), comparisons were made between TSS LRI images with and without normalization in range. The result for an ERS-2 SAR image is shown in Fig. 4. In far range (and very near range) the normalized image becomes brighter, while it becomes darker in near range. As can be seen from Fig. 5, the total range effects for an uniform surface is;

- in far range, the antenna pattern and the long distance to the target cause the signal to be weakened compared to mid-range,
- in near range, the antenna pattern and a shorter distance to the target cause the returned signal to be stronger here than for mid-range,
- in very near range, the antenna pattern again leads to a weakening of the signal compared to mid-range.

Figure 4: Comparison between a TSS LRI image without and with range normalization (a descending ERS-2 SAR image from 17 September 1995). The curves cross in mid range, and in very near range.

Figure 5: Difference between the two curves in Fig. 4, i.e. the range correction curve.

Comparison between TSS LRI and ESA PRI

As mentioned in the beginning of this appendix, TSS SAR products are delivered with only internal calibration applied. Since very little literature exist on correction and calibration of TSS SAR imagery, a test was performed to investigate the backscattering coefficient. For this purpose, a comparison was made between backscatter coefficients from ERS-1/2 SAR scenes obtained both as a TSS LRI product and as an ESA Precision Image (PRI) product. The latter has an estimated backscattering coefficient accuracy of ± 0.4 dB. The PRI image used at NERSC is corrected for all the above mentioned phenomena (including the powerloss due to ADC saturation) [Laur *et al.*, 1996]. Before a comparison could be performed, the PRI image was also averaged to 100m pixel size.

The differences between an ESA PRI scene and a TSS LRI scene are;

- The PRI includes ADC saturation correction
- Averaging methods:
 - LRI: Block averaging (5×5) PRI from 20×16 m to 100×80 m pixel size (range $\times$ azimuth). Then resampling by nearest neighbor interpolation to 100×100 m pixel size.
 - PRI: Block averaging (8×8) from 12.5×12.5 m to 100×100 m pixel size.
- The edge cutting in near and far range is different, due to correction and calibration algorithms. The PRI (100m pixel sized image) used in the IDL algorithms is 702×855 pixels, while the LRI is 990×1024 pixels.
- Different methods for calculation of the calibration constant K. The method used for LRI images is described in step 5 in the previous section, while the PRI images are delivered from ESA with a calibration constant K, estimated using transponders located in Flevoland (The Netherlands) [Laur *et al.*, 1993]. Transponders are ground instruments which relay the transmitted signal back to the SAR, after increasing the signal strength by electronic amplification.

When calculating backscatter coefficients from LRI and PRI images, the major discrepancies will be caused by the different methods for calculation of the calibration constant K, and the lacking ADC correction of the LRI images [Laur *et al.*, 1993].

To compare an ERS-1 SAR image, a descending scene from 23 September 1995 obtained off the southern coast of Norway, was used (Fig. 6). For large distributed targets with a high backscatter level, e.g. rough sea areas or towns, the Analogue to Digital Converter (ADC) is saturated and power is lost [Laur *et al.*, 1996]. In the present example the wind speed was 10m/s from the west, and ADC corrections should be applied before extracting absolute backscatter values. From Figs. 7-8, it can be seen that the difference between the LRI and

the PRI images is largest in near range. This agrees with previous studies by Laur *et al.* [1993], that ADC corrections decrease from near range to far range. The difference remains below 1.6dB. Some of this difference, especially in near range in Fig. 8, can be explained by difficulties of matching the two curves due to different averaging methods from full to low resolution imagery. When matching the two curves by the location of the high/low backscatter front in far range, the shape of the curves in near range are “out of phase”. The “out of phase” phenomenon accounts for an average of 0.2dB, but may in extreme cases give 1dB, difference in the LRI and PRI plots. Taking this into consideration, the overall difference between LRI and PRI remains less than 1.5dB, which was the maximum ADC power loss detected by Laur *et al.* [1993].

Figure 6: A descending ERS-1 image from 23 September 1995 (10:30GMT). Image size is 100×100 km. The arrows indicate the locations used for comparison.

Figure 7: (a) Comparison A between the descending ERS-1 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image from Fig. 6 (both are corrected and calibrated as mentioned above). The curves cross each other in far range. (b) The difference between the ERS-1 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image.

Figure 8: (a) Comparison B between the descending ERS-1 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image from Fig. 6 (both are corrected and calibrated as mentioned above). (b) The difference between the ERS-1 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image.

To compare an ERS-2 SAR image from TSS (LRI) and ESA (PRI), a descending scene from 17 September 1995 obtained off the southwestern coast of Norway, was used (Fig. 9). The local wind speed was $\leq 5\text{m/s}$ from the east, which is lower than for the ERS-1 SAR image (Fig. 6). This lower wind speed will cause a reduction in ADC saturation. Compared to the ERS-1 SAR, the ERS-2 SAR ADC saturation is much reduced. However, this would also be the case, even if the wind speed has been higher in the ERS-2 example. This is caused by a reduction in on-board gains for the ERS-2 SAR [Laur *et al.*, 1996]. Therefore, the increasing gap in near range between the PRI and LRI curves found for ERS-1 is disappeared in Fig. 10a for ERS-2. Apart from a little effect of the “out of phase” phenomenon, the difference between the LRI and PRI seems more stable (Fig. 10b). This “constant” difference is probably due to the different calibration constants, K , used in PRI and LRI imagery.

Figure 9: A descending ERS-2 image from 17 September 1995 (10:50GMT). Image size is $100 \times 100\text{km}$. The arrow indicates the location used for comparison.

ADC corrections for TSS LRI imagery will be implemented in the near future. Since the correction and calibration algorithms used on SAR imagery in this thesis do not include this ADC correction, special care was taken when encountering slicks in near range of ERS-1 SAR imagery obtained in rough weather. Moreover, to improve the calibration of the TSS LRI products further, experiments using e.g. transponders are required. The use of such transponders with known backscatter properties, will allow better estimates of the calibration constant, K .

Figure 10: (a) Comparison between an ERS-2 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image (both are corrected and calibrated as mentioned above). The image used here is from 17 September 1995 (descending). (b) The difference between the ERS-2 ESA PRI and TSS LRI image.

Appendix B: Oil related hot spots

The appendix lists the pollution sources registered in the data base developed in this work. It includes the following regions;

- the Norwegian Sea
- the North Sea
- Skagerak
- Kattegat
- the Baltic Sea

For the Baltic Sea, it has been difficult to locate coordinates for platforms and factories. However this work is ongoing, and the data base is subject to continuous updating. Fig. 1 shows the main oil related installations of the Norwegian Sea and the North Sea.

Figure 1: Locations of oil (or gas) related installations in the study area. Blue: Norwegian, yellow: UK, green: Dutch, and red: Danish.

Table 1: Norwegian installations/factories

Installation	Site type	Company	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
Loke	Underwater installation	Statoil	58.4357944	1.9296750
Odin	Production platform	ESSO	60.0769333	2.1657500
Ula	Production platform	BP	57.1114306	2.8473306
Ula P	Process platform	BP	57.1117556	2.8485694
Ula Q	Hotel platform	BP	57.1110750	2.8459833
Gyda	Production platform	BP	56.9049250	3.0851972
Gullfaks A	Production platform	Statoil	61.1761056	2.1891500
Gullfaks B	Production platform	Statoil	61.2029167	2.2013000
Gullfaks C	Production platform	Statoil	61.2149444	2.2738694
Statfjord A	Production platform	Statoil	61.2556830	1.8538750
Statfjord B	Production platform	Statoil	61.2069111	1.8306361
Statfjord C	Production platform	Statoil	61.2965833	1.9025472
Heimdal	Production platform	ELF	59.5741611	2.2288056
Frigg DP2	Production platform	ELF	59.8861306	2.0723889
Lille-Frigg	Underwater installation		59.9616389	2.3908333
Snorre P	Production platform	SAGA	61.4493361	2.1443444
Snorre Template	Underwater installation	SAGA	61.4893278	2.2263444
Froy			59.7341667	2.5577778
Tor	Production platform	Phillips	56.6420722	3.3269583
Ekofisk A	Production platform	Phillips	56.5210139	3.2228583
Ekofisk B	Production platform	Phillips	56.5653528	3.2036889
Ekofisk C	Production platform	Phillips	56.5478417	3.2155167
Ekofisk K	Injection platform	Phillips	56.5658028	3.2061056
Ekofisk W	Injection platform	Phillips	56.5441972	3.2179333
Ekofisk X		Phillips	56.5476389	3.2189444
Ekofisk D	Production platform	Phillips	56.5630569	3.0855556
Vest Ekofisk			56.5632083	3.0856000
Heidrun	Production platform	CONOCO	65.3258333	7.3175000
Heidrun C			65.2863889	7.3030556
Heidrun B			65.3127778	7.2625000
Draugen	Production platform	Shell	64.3531722	7.7798528
Draugen B	Underwater installation	Shell	64.4002639	7.7958167
Draugen C	Underwater installation	Shell	64.3107111	7.7384083
Mime	Underwater installation	Hydro	57.1201417	2.4862667
Tommeliten	Underwater installation	Statoil	56.4921278	2.9241917
Veslefrikk A	"Stigerørsplattform"	Statoil	60.7827056	2.8978583
Veslefrikk B	Production platform	Statoil	60.7827056	2.8978583
Albuskjell A	Production platform	Phillips	56.6428861	2.9400083
Albuskjell F	Production platform	Phillips	56.6205361	3.0539472
Eldfisk A	Production platform	Phillips	56.3768806	3.2658028
Eldfisk B	Production platform	Phillips	56.4193306	3.2183944

Table 1: (Continued)

Installation	Site type	Company	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
Vigdis			61.3805278	2.1032778
Hod	Underwater installation	AMOCO	56.1765333	3.4600611
Togi	Underwater installation	Hydro	60.5742500	3.6575278
Aasgard E			65.0438333	6.5954944
Aasgard F			65.0295000	6.6013083
Aasgard G			65.0882167	6.6623083
Aasgard H			65.1199306	6.6638667
Aasgard I			65.0853056	6.6818250
Aasgard J			65.1709528	6.7019528
Aasgard K			65.1340528	6.7045889
Aasgard L			65.1381778	6.7837361
Aasgard M			65.1764889	6.7784139
Aasgard N			65.1845694	6.8776556
Aasgard P			65.0230444	6.8790750
Aasgard R			65.0334222	6.9020389
Aasgard S			65.0160806	6.9458556
Aasgard X			65.0676417	7.4929944
Aasgard Y			65.0114639	7.5467472
Aasgard Z			64.9707000	7.6222194
Troll			60.6333351	3.6833334
Troll D			60.8567278	3.4448028
Troll E			60.7992167	3.4382444
Troll F			60.7761694	3.4382444
Troll G			60.7535222	3.4421417
Troll H			60.7144972	3.5103778
Troll A	Gas production platform	Norsk Hydro	60.6456389	3.7264944
Troll B	Production platform	Norsk Hydro	60.7743750	3.5031806
Yme			57.8187444	4.5196500
Yme B			57.7542500	4.3560556
Edda 2/7 C	Production platform	Phillips	56.4648389	3.1044639
Embla	Underwater installation	Phillips	56.3332306	3.2482639
Cod 7/11 A	Production platform	Phillips	57.0695528	2.4347222
Valhall	Production platform	AMOCO	56.2781639	3.3953306
Valhall-P	Process platform	AMOCO	56.2775556	3.3966389
Valhall-Q	Hotel platform	AMOCO	56.2788333	3.3942778
Valhall-WP			56.2765833	3.3963889
Oseberg A	Production platform	Hydro	60.4918639	2.8273139
Oseberg B	Production platform	Hydro	60.4933722	2.8285722
Oseberg C	Production platform	Hydro	60.6081722	2.7760000
Oseberg Vest			60.5410111	2.7192556
Draupner S			58.1887778	2.4726667
Trodis	Underwater installation	SAGA	61.2757389	2.1177194

Table 1: (Continued)

Installation	Site type	Company	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
Brage	Production platform	Hydro	60.5425389	3.0473972
Sleipner A	Production platform	Statoil	58.3673139	1.9086139
Sleipner D	Underwater installation	Statoil	58.3972028	1.9172083
Sleipner R	"Stigerørsplatform"	Statoil	58.3685639	1.9105306
Sleipner Vest			58.4179278	1.7178417
33/12-SPMB	"Lastebøye"	Statoil	61.2244167	1.8386444
33/9-SPMC	"Lastebøye"	Statoil	61.2810556	1.8838333
STATFJORD OST K	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.3439444	1.9727778
STATFJORD OST L	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.3294030	1.9865220
STATFJORD OST M	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.3412560	1.9998970
25/1-TCP2	Process platform	ELF	59.8801222	2.0665361
34/10-A-9H	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1767278	2.1492889
34/10-SPM1	"Lastebøye"	Statoil	61.1916056	2.1575083
25/1-B	Underwater installation	ELF	59.9865111	2.2493167
25/2-A	Underwater installation	ELF	59.9190694	2.3644417
25/2-B	Underwater installation	ELF	59.8906667	2.3629111
25/2-SMS	Underwater installation	ELF	59.9046417	2.3629111
34/10-A-1H	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1846472	2.2209750
34/10-A-2AH	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1801361	2.2184528
34/10-A-3H	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1872944	2.2114611
34/10-A-4H	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1882028	2.2242972
34/10-A-5H	Underwater installation	Statoil	61.1783694	2.2106750
34/10-SPM2	"Lastebøye"	Statoil	61.1672333	2.2297833
7/11-FL	Flame tower		57.0684833	2.4354222
30/6-T			60.5609722	2.8967778
30/9-B49H	Underwater installation	Hydro	60.5421500	2.8374222
30/9-B50H	Underwater installation	Hydro	60.5412139	2.8065556
2/7-ABS	Flame tower	Phillips	56.3746583	3.2665333
2/7-AFS	Flame tower	Phillips	56.3737583	3.2672611
2/7-FTP	Process platform	Phillips	56.3757194	3.2659333
2/4-FTP	Process platform	Phillips	56.5461806	3.2167389
2/4-G	"Stigerørsplatform"	Phillips	56.5491972	3.2099861
2/4-H	Hotel platform	Phillips	56.5472111	3.2131333
2/4-P	"Pumpeplatform"	Phillips	56.5486917	3.2136528
2/4-Q	Hotel platform	Phillips	56.5469806	3.2160306
2/4-R	"Stigerørsplatform"	Phillips	56.5506583	3.2117194
2/4-S	"Stigerørsplatform"	Phillips	56.5518972	3.2138167
2/4-T	Process platform	Phillips	56.5495417	3.2125806
2/7-BFS	Flame tower	Phillips	56.4182389	3.2194500
2/4-EFS	Flame tower	Phillips	56.6409389	3.32761677

Table 1: (Continued)

Installation	Site type	Company	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
STATFJORD A ALP			61.2635110	1.8872310
STATFJORD NORD D			61.4473611	1.9141667
STATFJORD NORD E			61.4342500	1.9251111
STATFJORD NORD F			61.4447222	1.9563333
STATFJORD G			61.3657139	1.9349833
West Vanguard	Floating rigs		64.2666667	7.2010000
Transocean Searcher	Floating rigs		65.1333333	6.7833333
Transocean 8 XTRA	Floating rigs		65.7540000	7.9196667
Transocean 8	Floating rigs		66.3050000	8.5166667
Ocean Alliance	Floating rigs		67.0666667	7.0060000
Factory Sirevåg	Fish processing plant		58.5042000	5.7446000
Oil refinery Valløy	Acid pitch disposal area		59.2485000	10.5571000

Table 2: Danish installations

Installation	Site type	Latitude	Longitude
Dan		55.4783333	5.1066666
Gorm C		55.5800000	4.7583333
Gorm F		55.5733333	4.7550000
Tyra E		55.7216666	4.8033333
Tyra W		55.7166666	4.7500000

Table 3: UK installations

Installation	Site type	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
AH001		58.1827777	0.1230555
Alwyn North		60.8097222	1.7361111
Auk		56.4005555	2.0633333
Balmoral		58.2291666	1.1088888
Beatrice		58.1150000	3.0866666
Beryl A		59.5463888	1.5372222
Beryl B		59.6102777	1.5130555
Brae A		58.6925000	1.2816666
Brae Nth		58.7922222	1.3475000
Brent B		61.0558333	1.7130555
Brent C		61.0961111	1.7216666
Brent D		61.1325000	1.7361111
Buchan		57.9036111	1.9333333
Claymore		58.4494444	0.2533333
Clyde		56.4527777	2.2886111
Cormorant A		61.1025000	1.0727777
Cormorant North		61.2405555	1.1494444
Dunlin		61.2750000	1.5975000
Eider		61.3572222	1.1611111
Emerald Producer		60.6833333	0.9333333
Forties A		57.7322222	0.9725000
Forties B		57.7494444	0.9150000
Forties C		57.7272222	0.8472222
Forties D		57.7225000	0.9030555
Fulmar A		56.4936111	2.1547222
Fulmar FSU		56.4927777	2.1552777
Gannet		57.1850000	1.0000000
Heather		60.9536111	0.9397222
N.W. Hutton		61.1066666	1.3091666
Hutton TLP		61.0688888	1.4025000
Kittiwake		57.4683333	0.5116666
Magnus		61.6200000	1.3069444
Maureen		57.1322222	1.7011111
Miller		58.7222222	1.4019444
Montrose		57.4505555	1.3877777
Murchinson		61.3969444	1.7405555
Ninian Central		60.8566666	1.4688888
Ninian Northern		60.9061111	1.4211111
Ninian Southern		60.8055555	1.4494444

Table 3: (Continued)

Installation	Site type	Latitude (°N)	Longitude(°E)
Piper		58.4616666	0.2500000
Seillean Miller		58.7216666	1.4016666
Tartan		58.3697222	0.0736111
Tern A		61.2761111	0.8361111
Thistle		61.3633333	1.5794444

Table 4: Dutch installations

Installation	Site type	Latitude	Longitude
P15C-PP RIJN C		52.2911111	3.8175000
K18-Kotter		53.0822222	3.9658333
L16-Logger		53.0150000	4.2175000
AWG-1-P		53.4927777	5.9416666
K14-FA-1P		53.2694444	3.6275000
K15-FA-1		53.2480555	3.9875000
K15-FB-1		53.2763888	3.8730555
K7-FA-1P		53.5727777	3.3050000
K8-FA-1		53.5000000	3.3702777
L13-FC-1P		53.2841666	4.2097222
L7-P		53.5380555	4.2033333
K12-BD-BP		53.3419444	3.8969444
K12-PA		53.4766666	3.7886111
K9-AB-A		53.5208333	3.9936111
Q1-Helder/Haven		52.9213888	4.0983333
Q1-Helm		52.8725000	4.1422222
Q1-Hoorn		52.9252777	4.1502777

Table 5: The Baltic Sea

Area				
No.	Location	Country	Site name	Site type
Bothnian Bay				
1	Bothnian Bay	Sweden	Rönnskärsverken	Industry (Metal Smelter)
2	Bothnian Bay	Finland	Metsä - Botnia Oy Kemi	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
Bothnian Sea				
3	Bothnian Sea	Sweden	Husum Kraft Mill	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
4	Bothnian Sea	Sweden	Östrand	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
5	Bothnian Sea	Sweden	Vallvik	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
6	Dalälven River	Sweden	Dalälven	Mining Waste
7	Bothnian Sea	Finland	Outokumpu Group Harjavalta	Industry (Metal Smelter)
8	Bothnian Sea	Finland	Kemira Oy Vuorikemia	Industry (Titanium oxide)
Archipelago and Åland Seas				
9	Arch. & Åland Seas	Finland	Fish Farming	Fish Farming
10	Archipelago Sea	Finland	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff
Neva River Basin / Lake Ladoga				
11	Lake Saimaa	Finland	YPT Joutseno	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
12	Lake Saimaa	Finland	Kaukas Lappeenranta	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
13	Lake Saimaa	Finland	E-G Kaukopä	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
14	Lake Ladoga	Russia	Syasstroi	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
15	Lake Ladoga	Russia	Volkhov	Industry (Aluminum)
Gulf of Finland				
16	Gulf of Finland	Finland	Sunila Oy - Kotka	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
17	Gulf of Finland	Finland	Helsinki Region	Municipal
18	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg	Connection Sewers
19	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg (Urban)	Municipal & Industrial
20	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg (Suburban)	Municipal & Industrial
21	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg	Phosphorous Removal
22	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg	Industry (Metal Plating)
23	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg	Hazardous Waste
24	Gulf of Finland	Russia	St. Petersburg Region	Large Livestock Farms
25	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Narva	Power Plants (Oil Shale)
26	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Kohtla Järve	Municipal & Industrial
27	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Kehra	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
28	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Tallinn	Municipal & Industrial
29	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Tallinn	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
30	Gulf of Finland	Estonia	Gulf of Finland	Agricultural Runoff Programme
Western Estonian Coast				
31	Estonian Coast	Estonia	Haapsalu	Municipal & Industrial
32	Estonian Coast	Estonia	Matsalu Bay	Management Programme

Table 5: Continued

Gulf of Riga / Daugava River Basin				
33	Gulf of Riga	Estonia	Pänu	Municipal & Industrial
34	Gulf of Riga	Estonia	Paide	Municipal & Industrial
35	Gulf of Riga	Estonia	Vohma Meat Combine	Industry
36	Gulf of Riga	Estonia	Gulf of Riga	Agricultural Runoff Programme
37	Gulf of Riga	Est./Lat.	Gulf of Riga	Management Programme
38	Gulf of Riga	Latvia	Sloka	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
39	Gulf of Riga	Latvia	Latbiofarm	Industry (Pharmaceutical)
40	Gulf of Riga	Latvia	Agriculture/Livestock	Agricultural Runoff Programme
41	Gulf of Riga	Lithuania	Siauliai	Municipal & Industrial
42	Daugava RB	Latvia	Riga	Municipal & Industrial
43	Daugava RB	Latvia	VEF Plant (Riga)	Industry (Metals)
44	Daugava RB	Latvia	RER Plant (Riga)	Industry (Metals)
45	Daugava RB	Latvia	Riga	Industry (Various)
46	Daugava RB	Latvia	Daugavpils	Municipal & Industrial
47	Daugava RB	Belarus		
Latvian Coast				
48	Latvian Coast	Latvia	Liepaja	Municipal & Industrial
Nemunas River Basin				
49	Nemunas RB	Russia	Sovetsk	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
50	Nemunas RB	Russia	Neman	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
51	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Kaunas	Municipal & Industrial
52	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Amalg Azotaz	Industry (Fertilizer)
53	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Kedainiai	Municipal & Industrial
54	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Kedainiai	Industry (Chemicals)
55	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Panevezys	Municipal & Industrial
56	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Panevezys	Industry (Food)
57	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Marijampole	Municipal & Industrial
58	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Alytus	Municipal & Industrial
59	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Vilnius/Grigiskes	Municipal & Industrial
60	Nemunas RB	Lithuania	Agriculture/Livestock	Agricultural Runoff Programme
61	Nemunas RB	Belarus	Grodno	Municipal & Industrial
Lithuanian Coast				
62	Lith. Coast	Lithuania	Mazeikiai	Oil Refinery Marine Termina
63	Lith. Coast	Lithuania	Klaipeda	Municipal & Industrial
64	Lith. Coast	Lithuania	Cardboard Factory	Industry (Paper)
65	Lith. Coast	Lithuania	Palanga	Municipal
Lithuanian / Kaliningrad Coast				
66	Lith/Kal Coast	Lith/Russi	Kursiu Lagoon	Management Programme
67	Kaliningrad	Russia	Kaliningrad	Municipal & Industrial
68	Kaliningrad	Russia		Industry (Pulp & Paper)
69	Kaliningrad	Russia		Industry (Pulp & Paper)

Table 5: Continued

70	Kaliningrad	Russia	Kaliningrad	Hazardous Waste
71	Kaliningrad	Russia	Oil Bunkering Station	Industry
72	Kaliningrad	Russia	Agriculture/Livestock	Agricultural Runoff Programme
Kaliningrad / Polish Coast				
73	Kal/Pol Coast	Russia/Pol	Vistula Lagoon	Management Programme
Vistula River Basin / Baltic Coast of Poland				
74	Baltic Coast	Poland	Kozalin	Municipal & Industrial
75	Baltic Coast	Poland	Gdynia-Debogorze	Municipal & Industrial
76	Baltic Coast	Poland	Gdansk-Wschod	Municipal & Industrial
77	Vistula	Poland	Swiecie	Industry (Pulp & Paper)
78	Vistula	Poland	Bydgoszcz-Fordon	Municipal & Industrial
79	Vistula	Poland	Bydgoszcz-Kapusciska	Industry (Chemical)
80	Vistula	Poland	Torun	Municipal & Industrial
81	Vistula	Poland	Wloclawek	Municipal & Industrial
82	Vistula	Poland	Warsaw-Czajka	Municipal & Industrial
83	Vistula	Poland	Warsaw-Siekierki	Municipal & Industrial
84	Vistula	Poland	Warsaw-Pancerz	Municipal & Industrial
85	Vistula	Poland	Lublin-Hajdow	Municipal & Industrial
86	Vistula	Poland	Krakow-Plaszow	Municipal & Industrial
87	Vistula	Poland	Krakow-Kujawy	Municipal & Industrial
88	Vistula	Poland	Katowice -East	Municipal & Industrial
89	Vistula	Poland	Jaworzno Organico Azot	Industry (Chemical)
90	Vistula	Poland	Zgierz-Boruta Dyestuffs	Industry (Chemical)
91	Vistula	Poland	Oswiecim-ZCHO Chem.	Industry (Chemical)
92	Vistula	Poland	Zaklady Gorniczo	Industry (Metals)
93	Vistula	Belarus	Brest	Municipal & Industrial
94	Vistula	Ukraine	Lvov	Municipal & Industrial
95	Vistula	Poland	Agriculture/ Livestock	Agricultural Runoff Programme
96	Vistula	Poland	Upper Basin	(Salt Control)
Oder-Odra River Basin				
97	Oder / Odra	Poland	Szczecin	Municipal & Industrial
98	Oder / Odra	Poland	Szczecin	Industry (Fert,Food,P&P)
99	Oder / Odra	Poland	Poznan	Municipal & Industrial
100	Oder / Odra	Poland	Lodz	Municipal & Industrial
101	Oder / Odra	Poland	Zielona Gora	Municipal & Industrial
102	Oder / Odra	Poland	Legnica-Glogow	Industry (N-Fer,Cu,Food)
103	Oder / Odra	Poland	Wroclaw	Municipal & Industrial
104	Oder / Odra	Poland	Wroclaw	Industry (Chem,Food,Textiles)
105	Oder / Odra	Poland	Ubocz-Luban	Industry (Fertilizer)
106	Oder / Odra	Poland	Boleslawiec	Industry (Fertilizer)
107	Oder / Odra	Poland	Katowice-West	Municipal & Industrial
108	Oder / Odra	Poland	Katowice-West	Industry

Table 5: Continued

109	Oder / Odra	CSFR	Ostrava	Municipal & Industrial
110	Oder / Odra	CSFR	Ostrava Area	Industry (Chem,P&P,etc.)
111	Oder / Odra	CSFR/Polan	Upper Basin	(Salt Control)
112	Oder / Odra	Poland	Agriculture/ Livestock	Agricultural Runoff Programme
113	Oder / Odra	Poland/Ger	Odra Lagoon mgt	Management Programme
Arkano Basin				
114	Arkona Basin	Germany	Greifswald	Municipal & Industrial
115	Arkona Basin	Germany	Neubrandenburg	Municipal & Industrial
116	Arkona Basin	Germany	Stralsund	Municipal & Industrial
117	Arkona Basin	Germany	Stavenhagen-Malchin	Municipal & Industrial
118	Arkona Basin	Germany	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
Belt Sea				
119	Belt Sea	Germany	Lbeck	Municipal & Industrial
120	Belt Sea	Germany	Wismar	Municipal & Industrial
121	Belt Sea	Germany	Rostock	Municipal & Industrial
122	Belt Sea	Denmark	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
The Sound				
123	The Sound	Denmark	Copenhagen	Municipal
124	The Sound	Denmark	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
125	The Sound	Sweden	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
Kattegat				
126	Gota elv River	Sweden	Skoghall	Industry, Pulp & Paper
127	Kattegat	Sweden	Goteborg	Municipal
128	Kattegat	Sweden	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
129	Kattegat	Denmark	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme
Swedish Coast				
130	Swedish Coast	Sweden	Stockholm	Municipal
Bornholm Basin				
131	Bornholm Basin	Sweden	Nymolla	Industry, Pulp & Paper
132	Bornholm Basin	Sweden	Agriculture	Agricultural Runoff Programme

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